

Osseointegration In Implants - An Update

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Abstract

The process of bone-implant interface formation refers to osseointegration. Unlike natural dentition, the anchorage is formed directly by bone to implant contact, which can be appreciated microscopically. It occurs within 4-6 months and is mandatory for long term success of implant therapy. This review article hence, explores the discovery, mechanism, criteria for assessing the success of osseointegrated implants, among other things, in detail.

Keywords : Osseointegration, implants, bone-implant interface

Introduction

The last five decades have seen the evolution of implant therapy, making it the most probable option for replacement of missing teeth. The reason behind its popularity as a treatment modality for edentulous and partially edentulous patients is that not only does it provide biological and functional advantages, but also produces long term results as observed by various authors in a 10 year follow up period. (Buser D et al., 2012 ,Degidi M et al., 2012 , Fischer K et al., 2012 , Gotfredsen K et al., 2012)^[1]

Professor P. I. Brånemark^[1] from the University of Gothenburg (Sweden), who performed the first preclinical and clinical studies in the 1950s, is considered as the foremost pioneer of modern implant dentistry. Another pioneer in the field is **Professor Andre Schroeder**^[1] from the University of Bern (Switzerland), who in the late 1960s, examined tissue integration of numerous implant materials and along with his team was the first to document bone-to-implant contact for titanium implants.

The word osseointegration consists of “os” the Latin word for “bone” and “integration” derived from the Latin words meaning ‘the state of being combined into a complete whole.’

Concept development

Per- Ingvar Brånemark^[2], conducted a study in the 1950s on microcirculation of rabbit bone and discovered that chambers made of metal titanium became perma-

nently anchored in bone. The bone became so infused with metal that the two couldn't be separated without fracture. Hence the concept was introduced. The term “osseointegration” was proposed by him in 1976 to describe this stable fixation between bone and titanium.

Definition

Brånemark defined it “as a direct contact between the bone and metallic implants, without interposed soft tissue layers” (1969). Later it was altered to “a direct structural and functional connection between ordered, living bone and the surface of a load carrying implant”^[3]

Dorland's illustrated Medical Dictionary 28th Edition^[4] : “Os-seo-in-te-gra-tion is direct anchorage of an implant by the formation of bony tissue around the implant without the growth of fibrous tissue at the bone-implant interface.”

“Contact established without interposition of non-bone tissue between normal remodeled bone and an implant entailing a sustained transfer and distribution of load from the implant to and within the bone tissue.” - American Academy of Implant Dentistry (1986)^[5]

“The apparent direct attachment or connection of osseous tissue to an inert, alloplastic material without intervening

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connective tissue.”-G.P.T. 8[6]

Mechanism of Osseointegration

It consists of^[7]

- A. Wound healing post surgical placement of implants depending on presence of adequate cells, adequate nutrition and stimulus for bone repair
- B. Inflammatory phase comprises vascular events wherein platelets after coming in contact with synthetic surface releases serotonin and histamine leading to platelet aggregation and thrombosis. This is followed by cellular events wherein neutrophils peak during 3-4 days and by the end of the first week the inflammatory response becomes more specific and there is an increase in T cells, B cells and NK cells.
- C. Proliferative phase consists of neovascularization. Local inflammatory cells create an area of relative hypoxia leading to differentiation of mesenchymal cells into fibroblasts, chondroblasts and osteoblasts. An extracellular matrix is laid down which converts into fibrocartilaginous callus and finally into bone callus, giving rise to woven bone.
- D. Maturation phase is when concurrent to formation of fibrocartilaginous callus, woven bone is laid down on scaffold of necrotic bone in peri-implant space. Simultaneous resorption and deposition, results in complete bone remodelling.

Thus mechanism of osseointegration can be subdivided into three biologic phenomena as described by J.E. Davies (1998), they are

A. Osteoconduction

Wilson-Hench, has suggested that “osteoconduction is the process by which bone is directed so as to conform to a material's surface.” Formation of bone on the implant surface is either done by the pre-existing pre osteoblasts/osteoblasts or through primitive mesenchymal cells via osteoinduction. (Frost HM (1989))^[8]

Bone growth factors and a proper blood supply are necessary for bone formation. Simultaneous process of osteoconduction and osteoinduction leads to osseointegration. Only the cells which reach the implant surface and then differentiate will lead to de novo bone synthesis. This ceases their migration. Other migratory cells continue to secrete bone along the implant surface as and when they come in contact. This histologically appears as “spreading” of bone over the implant surface.

- B. Osteogenesis (De novo bone formation) and bone bonding:

J.E. Davies et al (1996)[9] described the cascade of new bone formation in four different stages.

Stage 1 : The differentiating osteogenic cells initially secrete collagen free organ matrix with two non-collagen proteins osteopontin and bone sialoprotein.

Stage 2 : The organic matrix provides a nucleation site for calcium phosphate mineralization. The nucleation

will be found at the calcium binding sites of one or both of the prot-eins of the organic matrix.

Stage 3 : Calcium phosphate crystal growth takes place after nucleation and concomitantly there will be initiation of collagen fibre assembly at the developing interface.

Stage 4 : Finally calcification of individual collagen fibrils and collagen compartments take place and they are separated by a collagen free calcified tissue layer containing non collagen protein. This layer is 0.5 m thick and described by Davies (1998) as a cement line which was first described by a German histologist Von Ebner as 'Kittlinin or Cement lines', 123 years ago. This is the calcified interfacial matrix laid down between old and new bone.

C. Bone remodeling

The Stage of remodeling starts around 3rd month & becomes highly active for several weeks, then slows down again. It is of extreme importance for the long term stability of the transcortical plate of the endosseous implant, since cortical bone will necrose as a result of the surgical trauma to the tissue. As proposed by Forst, remodeling takes place as a discrete unit in both cortical and cancellous bone. Remodeling starts with osteoclastic resorption followed by lamellar bone deposition, so resorption and deposition of bone goes side by side to maintain the healthy skeletal mass.

Theories of bone-implant interface

Fibro-osseous integration

The American Academy of Implant Dentistry (1986)^[5] defined fibrous integration as “tissue-to-implant contact with healthy dense collagenous tissue between the implant and bone”. According to this theory the function portrayed by Sharpey's fibers in natural dentition, is fulfilled by collagen fibers between implant and bone surface. The difference between compression and tension of the connective tissue components results in a bioelectric current, and this current (a piezoelectric effect) induces differentiation into connective tissue components associated with bone maintenance.

Failure of theory : There was no real evidence to support the fact that the fibrous membrane present between the implant surface and bone, acted similarly to the periodontal ligament. Also, remodeling is not expected in fibrous integration as no forces are transmitted through the fibres. Absence of Sharpey's fibers at bone-implant interface leading to no transmission of load and hence no bone remodeling, is the primary reason this theory is not accepted currently.

Theory of Osseointegration

This theory was described as early as 1939 by Stroke, but gained recognition when documented by Braenmark in 1952. According to this theory the bone is formed in close contact to the immobile resting implant.

According to *Meffert et al (1987)*^[7] osseointegration maybe categorized into :

1. **Adaptive osseointegration** is where osseous tissue approximates the implant surface without the presence of soft tissue interface, as observed at light microscopic level

2. **Biointegration** is where a direct biochemical bone contact is observed at electron microscopic level.

It was observed that distribution of vertical and slightly inclined forces was achieved with osseointegration. If it fails to occur or is lost due to some reason, a fibrous connective tissue forms around the implant. In such conditions, the organization process continues against the implant material, possibly resulting from chronic inflammation and granulation tissue formation & osseointegration will never occur (Albrektsson et al, 1983)^[10]. A connective tissue interface may result due to premature loading of implant, too much pressure applied while placing the implant, overheating the bone during site

Osseointegration vs. Biointegration

According to *De Putter*^[11] implant anchorage may be of the following types :

A. Mechanical anchorage

- Seen in metallic implants
- Generated by interfacial tension of surface undercuts
- Anchorage is purely physical
- Direct contact between bone and metal surface

B. Bioactive retention

- Achieved when surface coated with bioactive material, such as hydroxyapatite
- Induces osteogenesis
- Physico chemical bond between metal surface and bone
- Similar to ankylosis

Implant Tissue Interface

Implant and Bone Interface^[12]

- At the light microscopic level, close adaptation of regularly organized bone next to the implant surface can be observed.
- Parallel alignment of lamellae of the Haversian system can be seen at SEM level.
- Absence of connective tissue and dead space at interface.
- Amorphous coats of glycoproteins on implants, to which collagen fibres are arranged at right angles and partly embedded in, can be observed at the interface, at ultra microscopic levels
- Cells do not bind directly to foreign materials, but attach via extracellular macromolecules. The glycoprotein layer is hence adsorbed on the implant surface by adhesive macromolecules like fibronectin, laminin, epinectin etc.
- Fibroblasts and other connective tissue cells contain a binding element known as integrin, through which they bond to the macromolecules.

Implant and connective tissue interface^[12]

- The attachment between connective tissue and implant is similar to bone-implant interface, that is, arranged parallel to implant surface.
- The attachment is not as strong as that seen in natural dentition, but is strong enough to withstand occlusal forces and microbial invasions.

Implant and Epithelial Interface^[12]

- Considered as biological seal
- Hemidesmosomes connect interface to plasma membranes of epithelial cells, making it closely similar to junctional epithelium.
- Sulcus depth for implants varies from 3-4 mm.

Factors Influencing Osseointegration

“There is a need to control these factors more or less simultaneously to achieve the desirable goal of a direct bone anchorage” (Albrektsson, 1983)

Implant biocompatibility

- Metals well covered with adherent, self-repairing and corrosion resistant oxide layers are well tolerated by bone. Eg. titanium, niobium.

A. Implant Design

- **Threaded implants** - Provide more surface area for stress distribution and better primary retention.^[13]
- **V-shaped threads** - Transfer forces in angulated paths.
- **Length** - Longer the implant better the primary stability.
- **Diameter** - Wider the implant, lesser the stress exerted on the crestal bone.
- **Implant neck** - providing micro threads helps maintain marginal bone.
- **Providing a Morse taper** - to reduce potential bacterial penetration at junction.^[14]
- **Platform switching** - Narrow diameter abutment over wide diameter implant, results in adequately dimensioned biological width, hence, reducing bone resorption.

B. Implant surface

- Related to degree of roughness and orientation of surface irregularities.
- Increased surface roughness ensures more bone on the implant leading to stronger anchorage.^[15]

C. State of the host bed

- Bone quality helps predict the long term success of implants
- Misch^[16] suggests “D1 and D2 bone densities show good stability and osseointegration compared to D3 and D4.”
- Fugazzotto et al (1993)^[17] documented that implants tend to fail more in D4 density bone as compared to D1, D2 or D3.

D. Surgical Considerations^[18]

- Surgical technique opted should aim towards regenerative rather than reparative form of healing
- Sharp drills
- Appropriate cooling period to avoid necrosis of bone
- Slow drill speed with irrigation
- Use of moderate power at implant insertion.

E. Loading conditions^[19]

- **Progressive or two stage loading** : According to Braenmark in order to attain osseointegration, loading of implant should be done post 3-6 months.
- **Immediate or one stage or non submerged loading** - here the implant is loaded with a provisional restoration immediately after placement or shortly thereafter.
- Fibrous integration may occur due to premature loading which may also result in loss of function.
- Methods of evaluation of osseointegration

Rigid fixation^[7]

- Absence of observed clinical mobility
- Movement of < 73 μ (clinically which appears as zero), is a sign of healthy implant.
- Checked with 2 rigid instruments applying a force labio lingually with a force of 500g
- Rated on a scale of 0-4 based on the criteria provided by Misch^[16].
- It is a specific, but not a sensitive, clinical parameter to assess osseointegration. Presence of mobility represents a late sign of implant failure.

Scale	Description
0	Absence of clinical mobility with 500 g in any direction
1	Slight detectable horizontal movement
2	Moderate visible horizontal mobility up to 0.5 mm
3	Severe horizontal movement greater than 0.5 mm
4	Visible moderate to severe horizontal and any visible vertical movement

Invasive Methods^[7]

1. **Histological sections** - Considered gold standard. But due to its invasive procedure and ethical issues, other methods may be used.
2. Histomorphometric
3. Transmission electron microscopy
4. Pull out tests.
5. By using torque gauges

Non-invasive Methods^[7]

1. **Percussion test** - Osseointegrated implant produces a ringing sound compared to a fibrous integrated implant which generates a dim sound
2. **Radiographic examination**
3. **Reverse torque test** : an unscrewing torque is applied and if the implant rotates, it is considered as a failure.
4. **Periotest**
5. **Resonance frequency analysis** : using vibration and structural analysis measures bone density and implant stability. The implant stability quotient (ISQ) varies between 40-80. Higher the value means higher the stability.

Evaluation of Success of Osseointegration

1. Schnitman and schulman 1979^[20]
2. Cranin et al. 1982^[21]
3. McKinney et al. 1984^[22]
4. Albrektsson Success Criteria (1986)^[23]
5. Smith D.E et al 1989^[24]

Albrektsson Success Criteria (1986)

1. Clinically, implants should be immobile.
2. On radiographic examination, radiolucency should be absent.
3. Post loading, 0.2 mm vertical bone loss is admissible, after the first year.
4. There should be no signs of pain, inflammation or paresthesia.
5. Success rate : 85% - 5 years and 80% - 10 years.

Factors responsible for failure of osseointegration

- Failures may occur due to “inadequacy of host tissue to establish or maintain osseointegration.”^[25]
- Esposito et al (1998)^[26] defined “biological failures related to biological process, and mechanical failures related to fractures of components and prostheses.”
- Koutsonikas (1998)^[27] added the categories of “iatrogenic failure and failure due to patient adaptation.”
- El Askary et al (1999)^[28] further defined failure as “ailing, failing, or failed implants.”
- Factors responsible may be related to implants, patients local or systemic factors or due to the surgical technique or environmental conditions.^[25]

Conclusion

Dental implants have paved the way for easy restoration of missing teeth and future advancements and technology should aim towards incorporating features ensuring osseointegration and hence achieving long term success of implants.

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